

THE ADVANTAGES OF AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING AND DEVELOPMENT METHODS OF THE ARTISTIC AND TECHNICAL SKILLS OF STUDENTS IN VISUAL ARTS CLASSES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10581694>

Abstract. *This article discusses the advantages of an innovative approach to teaching and methods of developing students' artistic and technical skills in art classes and a new approach to art classes.*

Keywords: *interactive methods, artistic and technical skills, non-traditional teaching methods, traditional teaching methods, innovative technologies, scientific and technical, subject, expert.*

The main essence of innovative pedagogical technology in teaching is the formation and development of positive qualities and qualities in each person based on his needs, interests, talents and capabilities. In this place, the content of education is considered an environment for the formation and development of a person. Therefore, the content of education should incorporate an innovative approach to humanity, humanistic ideas and norms.

In the educational process, teaching methods are carried out in different forms (individual, pair, group, large group). By satisfying the need for learning, the learning process becomes highly motivated.

Educational material is better remembered through mutual information giving, receiving, and processing. A student's self-evaluation and critical view develops during the learning process. For the student, the lesson becomes an interesting content of the taught subject. A creative approach to the study process, a positive thought is manifested. It leads to the ability of each student to think independently, to search, to observe.

When the lessons are conducted in an interactive way, the student not only learns the educational content, but also develops his critical and logical thoughts. Therefore, in such conditions, it is necessary for the teacher to have a highly developed thinking ability, a deep observation of problems, and the ability to solve problems in a timely manner.

When organizing a lesson in interactive methods, the development of the student's personality should begin with creating a foundation for himself. That is, the student:

- Independent reading and learning based on reading;
- Self-realization, self-education;
- To look confidently at one's strength and capabilities;
- To look at academic work with a sense of responsibility;
- To be able to independently organize one's activities, to enjoy every minute;
- To be able to arouse desire and desire for educational work;

- Be able to show activity in any situation;
- In particular, it is necessary to learn to make effective use of current information sources as the main and main goal.

The question of what is the purpose of using non-traditional teaching methods, what are its advantages and the principles of improving the effectiveness of the lesson can be answered based on the following properties. Non-traditional teaching is the simplest and most convenient method.

5. Teaches students to think independently.
6. Multidisciplinary.
7. Simple and easy.
8. Increases students' knowledge.
9. Wins over time.
10. The class will be interesting.
11. Increases the effectiveness of the lesson.
12. Expands students' outlook.
13. The student develops the thinking of young people.
14. Attracts the attention of students.
15. Treats each student individually.
16. Strengthens memory.
17. Invites to search.
18. Invites students to work on themselves.

The goal of education, i.e. teaching, is to convey the knowledge and skills specified in the state educational standards to the student. Teaching can be considered successful only when the knowledge is accepted and understood by the student, or the student can demonstrate in practice the tasks intended for skill improvement.

Pedagogical technology based on the humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations in the development of artistic and technical skills is fundamentally opposed to the technology of individual administration and creates a favorable environment for personal development and creativity through cooperation, care, respect and honoring the personality of students in the pedagogical process. In traditional education, the teacher (pedagogue) is considered to be the subject of the content of education, and students are considered to be the object of the pedagogical process, while in cooperative pedagogy, the student is considered to be the subject of his own educational activity. Therefore, in cooperative pedagogy, two subjects of a single educational process jointly solve educational tasks.

The idea of humanitarianism, aimed at forming and developing a complete human personality, occupies an important place in the center of the education system of this pedagogical technology in fine arts classes. The extent to which this idea has been implemented is determined based on the evaluation of the quality of the work of the pedagogical team, the main result of the educational process. An important factor determining the main result of the educational process in the humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations is the attitude towards the individual.

In the process of using methods in a certain style in fine arts classes, the status of each action is subordinated to specific goal indicators. In addition, a person follows a number of laws as a principle in the process of reaching the goal.

The educational method is a pedagogical event that systematizes the interactions between the teacher (pedagogue) and the pupils-students for the purpose of imparting and receiving knowledge. Teaching methods are the main part of the learning process. Pedagogical activities cannot be carried out without appropriate methods.

Styles are divided into verbal, demonstrative and practical, electronic, depending on the nature of knowledge transfer and reception. In mastering the educational content, the following methods are used in accordance with the educational activities of students: explanatory - illustrative, reproductive, problem statement, private search or heuristic and semi-research methods.

Problem-search methods are used in the process of problem-based education. When using these methods, the teacher (pedagogue) first creates a problem situation, asks questions, proposes problems, assignments, organizes a discussion aimed at solving the problem situation, and confirms the correctness of his conclusions. Based on their previous knowledge and experience, students make suggestions on ways to solve a problem situation, summarize their previously acquired knowledge, and choose the most reasonable option for solving a problem situation. This method not only increases students' interest in knowledge, but also develops their thinking ability. The development of any educational subject does not begin by itself. The theoretical rules of creating an academic pictorial work of the 17th century began to be expressed in the interpretations of Renaissance artists. The theory of academic teaching, which arose in the 18th century, underwent certain changes, and now artistic practice is carried out in new conditions. In the 19th century, active research on the comprehensive solution of educational issues in academic theory and practice began.

In the academic direction of the art school, it is envisaged not only to arm students with knowledge and skills, but also to participate in creative and innovative activities. If he gets a good education in higher education, is inquisitive and innovative, then he will become a mature staff for schools.

The Japanese say that if you teach yourself, you will remember 90% of what you learn. If teachers only stand and lecture, students remember much less - say 40 percent - so it's very helpful to discuss problems and debate with each other. Such methods and techniques are also used in practical training, so that students learn from each other and share experiences. A pedagogue who knows how to teach someone is formed by himself.

The representatives of the old academic school advised: "When you draw a picture from nature, do not directly copy everything that you see, but think about why it is like that, think about what is not different".

In modern society, innovative technologies are expanding in almost all spheres of human activity, including education. Innovations in education - a new field of scientific and pedagogical knowledge; three main pedagogical processes in the field of education: creation of innovations, their assimilation and application are inseparable unity and interdependence.

It is known that modernizing the educational process in higher education institutions, in particular the visual art educational process, developing the professional competence of teachers in raising the quality level of the system of training specialists who will become artist-pedagogues, making them relevant to the field Arming with modern professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, independently of scientific and technical innovations, creative use and development of skills to solve prospective tasks are considered important tasks.

As can be seen from the above points, the modernization of visual art education processes (visual modern-updated, modern) requires an innovative approach to the educational process in the areas of visual art and engineering graphics.

Organization of fine art classes in educational institutions using new modern innovative methods. In this regard, the requirements for professional and professional training of future visual arts teachers and ways of their implementation were studied.

As a result of studying the scientific-theoretical foundations of the development and introduction of innovative methods in education, it was determined that the following should be paid attention to:

- It is necessary to sufficiently use modern pedagogical technologies and innovative methods in the training of specialists in fine art classes;
- Formation of new content of education, introduction of new pedagogical technologies;
- Application and improvement of innovative methods in fine arts classes.

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